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How can AI augment aviation pilot training to enhance safety?

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1. Abstract

Statistics on flying incidents worldwide point that human errors are a major cause of aviation accidents. Article from “**Research Gate**” titled “**Human Factors in Aviation**”¹ state that there has been a decrease in the occurrence of incidents resulting from technical failures; however, incidents arising from human factors issues have emerged as the predominant underlying cause of most incidents. Several studies have investigated human factors issues in aviation. On review of the root cause of few of the aviation accidents in the past point out that is only through enhanced training of aircraft pilots – the risk of human factor can be reduced. This study explores the role of AI in improving pilot training to enhance aviation safety. In this study we review the benefits of training using the new generation of flight simulators that are fitted with enhanced visual systems, high-fidelity motion platforms integrated with AI and machine learning. These simulators use Virtual Reality (VR) & Augmented Reality (AR) to create realistic and dynamic scenarios that mimic a typical flight journey in real time from take -off to landing. These simulators can also simulate emergency situations to help practice and improve decision making to handle unforeseen situations. This immersive experiential training helps pilots in better situational awareness, builds their muscle memory and offers intuitive understanding of flight dynamics and its control system.

These simulators have advanced computer power and on coupling with AI can leverage large datasets collected from previous flight operations and training simulations. This data is analysed to identify common error patterns and optimize training protocols. The AI system then facilitates adaptive learning by providing feedback on pilot performance in real-time, enabling pilots and instructors to focus on areas that need improvement.

The study concludes that the use of AI in aviation training helps to improve pilot competence, confidence, and a better sense of control through enhancing their situational awareness thus reducing the chances of human errors leading to improvement in aviation safety.

¹ [Human Factors in Aviation. An overview](#)

2. Literature Review

Aircraft pilots have a huge responsibility to safely fly people every day from one place to another. Flying has inherent risks at all stages from take-off to landing and pilots undergo rigorous training and competency assessment until approved to fly an aircraft starting as a co-pilot alongside an experienced senior pilot. Most of the pilot training schools operate independently from the airline operators and are still using legacy platforms with outdated avionics which require separate conversion training. These schools still use cockpits that are fitted with outdated FTD (flying training devices) that offer procedural training but do not replicate the physical sensations of the flight – thus limiting their effectiveness for operational preparedness. Even though pilot training on legacy platform is quite comprehensive. It has its own limitations as it cannot simulate many unforeseen conditions such as varying external weather conditions or sudden technical glitches of aircraft components. Such gaps in Aircraft Pilot Training impacts the responsiveness and readiness of the pilots to handle situations which they have not encountered during the training. Despite airline operators investing in modern state-of-the-art aircraft in line with technological advancements, the pilot training is still outsourced from external training academies.

It is important to understand the types of risks which remain unmitigated while flying an aircraft and research the latest methods of AI based Pilot training using machine learning and personalized training plans and impact of enhanced AI based training on safety through improving pilots' competence, confidence & composure and reducing (cockpit stress) mental stress faced by the Pilots.

The time between the launch of new technologies and its adaptation has reduced drastically and there are numerous articles on how AI is being integrated into Pilot training to enhance their skills to improve aviation safety. It will be useful to identify the technology players in this field and who are the early adopters of such training who are bringing in innovation to this industry and summarize the benefits of such training.

AI can help to simulate training for the pilots to handle a variety of emergency situations through practising standard operating procedures (SOP's) and responses to handle crisis-like situations without any consequences in a controlled environment. The experience gained from such simulated training will equip the pilots to have clarity on mitigating such scenarios with quick thinking in implementing corrective set of actions. The adaptive AI training environment using cutting edge flight

simulators will enhance pilot competence, confidence through raising their alertness, improved concentration, sharpen their reflexes and learn to maintain a calm composure to overcome challenging flight conditions. This will enhance the safety and reduce the risks.

We do know that not all situations can be created in a classroom or training cockpit; however, we all know that Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) can be used to provide an immersive training experience to the pilots to improve their responsiveness and skills which can enhance the safety. The fact that AI driven flight simulators can create real-life scenarios with great accuracy is much better than conventional simulators and thus can prepare pilots to handle the uncertainties of real flights. It will be beneficial to harness the potential of AI in pilot training needs close collaboration between aviation training providers, civil aviation authorities as well as technology companies. The study will summarize how AI based training can prepare the pilots to handle any situation through personalized training with real time feedback on pilot performance.

Article from **AI Labs**² state that the journey from traditional cockpit-based training to high-fidelity simulators marks a significant evolution in pilot training methodologies. With the flight simulation market projected to reach USD 15.99 billion by 2032, the stage is set for a transformative shift. Today, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is poised to revolutionize this domain further, offering simulations that are more realistic, adaptive, and comprehensive than ever before. This transformation not only promises to elevate the quality of training but also to address the growing complexity of modern aviation challenges.

The missing factor is the lack of regulatory framework and will of the civil aviation authorities in implementing such training programs. Further research can consider more accurate cost estimates as well as list the infrastructure required by the aviation industry to deploy such AI based trainings.

² [AI-Enhanced Pilot Training and Simulation](#)

3. Introduction

Aircraft pilots undergo rigorous technical training, simulator-based training and on the job training as a co-pilot to a senior pilot as part of their course to learn and operate an aircraft safely. The training is followed by competency assessment and test flights under experience pilots to provide feedback and improvement areas.

Things happen fast in an airliner. An airliner can exceed ground speeds by more than 750 mph, and a pilot must be able to think faster than the speed of the aircraft he/she is flying. Get behind the aircraft, and it will blindly fly you into the ground or the side of a hill. The spatial understanding of operating a very fast vehicle in three (3) dimensions in fact four (4), if including time requires very special skill sets that can only be mastered through training. Adding the extra dimensions greatly complicates the problem, as the pilots not only have to master the horizontal, but also the vertical. Failure to be proficient in operating an airplane in 4 dimensions, or in staying ahead of the airplane, is the number one cause of flying accidents. Mastery of roll, pitch and yaw are also added to the equation, plus a pilot always must know exactly where they are always in relation to the world.

Conventional training methods do not simulate all scenarios such as external weather conditions or sudden technical glitches of aircraft components leading to limitation of exposure and split-second response required to handle such unforeseen conditions. The aviation pilot skill training and development infrastructure has seen a massive transformation through the introduction of next generation computing systems, cutting edge flight simulators which offer a “virtual cockpit” that have enhanced the quality of training and reduce cost and time required to be a competent pilot. AI driven flight simulators can create real-life scenarios with great accuracy much better than prior version of the simulators. **AI's role in pilot training is set to grow, with potential expansions into Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) to offer even more immersive training experiences with realism not possible earlier.**³

Companies like **Dedicated Computing** who specialize in creating integrated hardware, software, and services for all fidelity systems that process data to meet the demand of the next generation of flight training simulators. These all-fidelity systems are needed to produce realistic graphics in high-

³ [Trends in Aircraft Training Simulation](#)

resolution displays. Immersion in a training environment starts with accurate scenery reproduction. Such training offers greater interactive real time preparedness. It is to be noted that AI is being integrated into training as a collaborative tool, acting as an intelligent co-pilot during simulations. This "human-AI teaming" also called as Human Computer Interaction (HCI) enhances decision-making by providing pilots with much better situational awareness, real-time suggestions based on machine learning algorithms trained on historical flight data.

The ability of latest flight simulators to simulate real-world and dynamic situations including a range of emergencies drills mimicking extreme bad weather or failure of multiple instruments or components. This exposure is extremely valuable as it prepares the pilots to practise controls and actions required to handle a wide range of contingencies by quick corrective actions. There has been a marked improvement pilot concentration, reflexes including the ability to maintain a calm composure which will help them to overcome challenging flight conditions. In the future the industry will be able to see measurable improvement in aviation safety performance.

4. Research review

Flying has inherent risks at all stages from take-off to landing with statistics from reliable sources like **Aviation Safety Network, National Transport safety Board and Panish** indicating highest percentage of aircraft accidents happen during take-off and landing. Further in-depth data analysis reveal that human errors are a major cause of aviation incidents almost accounting for 50% of the aircraft accidents.

Source : www.panish.law

Loss of control remains a leading cause of aviation accidents, particularly in general aviation and during critical flight phases. Factors contributing to LOC-I include aerodynamic stalls, spatial disorientation, and improper aircraft handling. The modern-day pilots undergo rigorous training in aircraft, upset recovery techniques, stall recognition, and recovery procedures to mitigate the risk of LOC-I. Flight simulators and training devices provide pilots with realistic scenarios to practise recovery maneuvers and enhance their proficiency in handling unexpected situations.

Human error resulting from distraction and not following procedures. On **31st August 1999, LPA airlines Flight 3142 – a Boeing aircraft 737-204 C crashed** ⁵during take-off from Jorge Newbery Argentina as it failed to get airborne. The aircraft overshot the runway, broke the airports fence, then

⁴ [Aviation and Plane Crash Statistics | Updated 2025](#)

⁵ [Crash of a Boeing 737-204C in Buenos Aires: 65 killed | Bureau of Aircraft Accidents Archives](#)

crossed a road hitting a car on the way before collision with road construction equipment and highway median. Resulting fuel spill on the hot engine and gas leak from a damaged gas station resulted in a fire that destroyed the aircraft. There were 65 fatalities out of 105 onboard the aircraft and two people also died in the car that aircraft had hit.

The **American National Transportation Safety Board (NTSB)** concluded that plane had undergone regular maintenance, the engines were working as they should have prior to crash with construction equipment and that everything was working fine. Further investigation led to discovery that the plane failed to take off as the Pilots had forgotten to extend the wing flaps to initiate the take-off and even ignored the alarm advising them of the error in configuration for take-off. Lack of crew discipline, excessive conversations not relevant to the flight, failure to read the checklist properly, failure to abort take off after the alarm sounded and a failure by Boeing to fit an alarm that crew did not need to respond to it were noted as the main reasons for the crash.

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The approximate path of the Lapa Flight 3142 – breaking through the fence, the road and ending on a golf course

Source: Lapa Flight 3142 Wikimedia commons

⁶ [Source: Category:LAPA Flight 3142 - Wikimedia Commons](#)

Gaps in training to attend to an unforeseen fault in the aircraft. Investigators of a 2018 fatal accident in New Zealand reported that the pilot training did not include correct use of the auto/manual switch of a MD 600N helicopter. It was further reported that there were still gaps in the training which left the pilot unprepared to deal with fluctuating rotor speed caused by a faulty engine control unit and this pilot had almost 10,000 hours of flying experience. The fault resulted in a hard forced landing that killed one passenger.⁷

Fatal crash of MD 600N helicopter in New Zealand- Source: Transport Accident Investigation Commission (TAIC)

⁷ [TAIC reports on 2018 fatal helicopter forced landing of MD600N helicopter | TAIC](#)

⁸ Source: Transport Accident Investigation Commission (TAIC)

Adopting AI in Aviation pilot training to enhance safety. The new generation of flight training simulators are run by engineered high-fidelity computing systems thus integrating hardware, software and services. These high-fidelity systems facilitate realistic training experiences by closely mirroring actual flight scenarios and thus allowing the student pilots to self-train in a diverse range of commands and controls to handle a flight. These systems offer highly immersive training environment with precise scenery reproduction using high-resolution displays which produce realistic graphics. These simulators have features to replicate difficult terrain, variable weather scenarios, different types of runways, practice aircraft landing and take-off mimicking different times of the day.⁹

Aviation pilot training providers like **SkyArt and RedBird Flight** are offering advanced simulator-based training that has transformed the aviation pilot training. Their flight simulators that can mimic motion and control a real aircraft. The modern-day flight simulators now have cutting edge flight simulation technology which can **mimic sensation of motion and control into these interactive cockpits**. These simulators utilize enhanced reality, high-precision head & hand tracking, and the accurate, tactile feel and physical experience of the aircraft's flight controls and flight instruments and displays. The simulators integrate specific movements of an aircraft within the compact mini-motion platform fitted with 360^o Field of View visuals that deliver high-fidelity, physics-based simulation. The multi-axis motion systems can accurately replicate the physical sensations of a flight including replicating the forces alongside simulating takeoffs and landing thus enhancing the realism.¹⁰

A user learning to pilot a Boeing 737 will be constrained within the simulator by the maximum 20,600 pounds of thrust and static G-forces ranging from +2.5g to -1.0g, just like they would be in real life. The ability of Flight simulators to connect to live air traffic control tower. From review of historic aviation crash data, take-off and landing are the most complex phases for an airplane. Nearly 50% of all aviation accidents take place during landing and take-off procedures. This phase of the flight is very tough as crew managing airplane configuration changes from their last flight, navigate the plan

⁹ [Trends in Aircraft Training Simulation](#)

¹⁰ [The Art of Flight Simulation: Creating Realistic Training Environments | SkyArt](#)

at the airport, waiting to take off and land, communicating with air traffic control (ATC) while keeping an eye on the weather.

The new generation **Air Traffic Control simulator from FSHud** equipped with high-fidelity systems using onboard high speed computer processors can connect to live air traffic control towers and provide data in real time for the student pilot to interpret. This provides hands-on authentic flying experience as it can simulate the presence of other aircraft in the vicinity. Virtual, real-time airspace training allows pilots to safely practise communication with air traffic control as if they were in the air.

Source : FS Hud Air traffic control website ¹¹

Simulation of complex scenarios: AI driven flight simulators can create real-life scenarios with great accuracy much better than legacy simulators and thus can prepare pilots to manage the uncertainties of real flights. The features to mimic emergency along with flight data analytics enhance readiness of the pilots for a variety of challenges to handle extreme weather and instrument failures. Such adaptability fosters better decision-making and risk management skills during critical situations.

¹¹ [FSHud - Air Traffic Control: Realistic ATC for Microsoft Flight Simulator 2024 / 2020](#)

Pilots face challenging situations in the air like technical glitches, extreme weather conditions like landing during strong crosswinds at night and hence the pilot must be skilled, competent, fully alert and trained to take decisions within seconds to land or abort safely. The ability of the AI-based training simulators empowers the pilots to experience and learn how to maneuver the aircraft in such unforeseen situations in the safety of a virtual cockpit. This training environment helps the pilots to learn steps and procedures and practise mitigating actions with minimal risks. They can repeatedly practise, rehearse and test themselves until they gain the required level of competence and confidence.

Simulation of complex scenarios

AI's role in pilot training is set to grow, with potential expansions into Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) as it offers immersive training experiences with realism not possible earlier. The greater interactive real time training ensures better preparedness and alertness of the pilots. AI driven flight simulators can create real-life scenarios with great accuracy much better than legacy simulators and thus can prepare Pilots to handle the uncertainties of real flights.

The features to mimic emergency along with flight data analytics enhance the readiness of the pilots for a variety of challenges to handle extreme weather and instrument failures. Such adaptability fosters better decision-making and risk management skills during critical situations

Integration of gaming technologies

The modern generation virtual cockpit systems offer many novel improvements over the conventional simulators. With the use of VR pilot is exposed to a spatial environment with lifelike 3D effects. The VR pilot training offers a 360-degree view of the surroundings in addition to the depth of the view.

These features within the virtual cockpit provide better perception to the trainee pilots to get an appreciation and understanding of distances, heights, and spatial position of the aircraft from other objects and shapes.

Augmented Reality (AR) alongside Virtual Reality (VR) offers immersive experience to the student pilots and trains them in required steps (controls and protocols) to overcome unforeseen situations.

Such technologies improve the skills and knowledge of the student pilots, as they can practise taxis, take off, fly and land an aircraft and gain experience in a realistic environment.

VR technology being used at BAA Training

Augmented Reality (AR) systems are improving alongside the advancement in the new generation of flight simulators from companies like **BAA Training** that can transform the learning environment as per the needs of the user. These simulators can seamlessly transfer between cockpits of different make and model within the Virtual Reality (VR) systems by switching out the **rudder, stick, and throttle**. The same user training to pilot that Boeing 737 will soon be able to easily switch the virtual aircraft cockpit to practise on another model / make of the aircraft. Cutting-edge flight simulators equipped with advanced computing, machine learning, data processing and AI capabilities have revolutionized the flight training as it now permits the pilots to practise in real time, which was not possible earlier.

Training the pilots in the use and interpretation of real time weather data. **Full Motion simulators from Avenger Flight Group** are capable of environmental simulation which then helps to train the pilots how to overcome unpredictable weather patterns that can impact aircraft performance and safety. They must learn to fly in weather conditions, including thunderstorms, icing, turbulence, and low visibility, which pose significant risks to flight operations.

¹² [VR for Flight Training](#)(BAA Training website)

The advanced training simulators can connect to real time weather data and allow the pilots to receive extensive training in weather interpretation, risk assessment and decision-making to mitigate weather-related hazards. Advanced weather forecasting technologies and real-time weather monitoring systems provide pilots with accurate and timely information to plan routes and avoid hazardous weather conditions. The **Bravo 6 Flight Academy** gives special importance to providing training to handle diverse weather conditions.

Full Motion Flight Simulators – Avenger Flight Group

Lufthansa Aviation Training Germany is developing data-based training using AI in partnership with **CAE and Brussels Airlines** where the data (training data and operational manuals) is hosted in a cloud environment with support of Microsoft. During the training the pilots can access the data via a chat or voice interface.¹⁴

The latest AI agents mimic expert pilot's actions to train the new pilots in a simulated environment. These AI agents run on super computers hosting vast amounts of data and run on algorithms built by aviation experts to help augment decision making skills of the pilots. AI offers continuous learning

¹³ [Airbus A320 / A330 Full Flight Simulator - Avenger Flight Group](#)

¹⁴ [FFS Airbus A350-900 \(FT72\) - lufthansa-aviation-training.com](#)

opportunities with real time visual and corrective feedback comparing their performance to optimal standard operating procedures (SOP's), this helping the trainees refine their skills in real time thorough practise , repetition and analysis of their performance.¹⁵

This builds greater level of competence and confidence in the pilots who are then better equipped to respond to complex highly dynamic situations through well-informed decision making while always maintaining control of the flight.

Many technology companies are taking a leading role in innovation in AI based training with measurable benefits for example Innovations from **Massachusetts Institute of Technology "Air-Guardian"** a computer program that can track where human pilot is looking (using eye-tracking technology) so it can better understand what the pilot is focusing on. These tools enhance human-machine collaboration can significantly improve a pilot's situational awareness and response accuracy. The air guardian system act as a proactive co-pilot by guiding the pilots with visual cues if they overlook something especially during critical moments.¹⁶

AI Labs based out of California, USA has developed AI based enhanced pilot assistance (APAS) with features like autopilot systems, obstacle detection and automated landing improve pilot safety and mission success. This system can also monitor pilot behavior for signs of fatigue, stress or performance issues ensuring peak performance during the missions.

Pace Aerospace Engg. & Information Technology based in Berlin , Germany and branches all across the world offer data-driven pilot training that delivers better results in less time. They work with OEM's, airlines and training centers to help accelerate data drive competency-based training while reducing cost and time to train.

The Airline Pilot Club (APC) based out of Ireland has launched Amelia, an artificial intelligence (AI) platform aimed at enhancing aviation recruitment and training processes. Unveiled at EATS 2024, Amelia is designed to improve operational efficiency and reduce costs for airlines and flight schools by incorporating advanced AI technology into their systems.

¹⁵ [Data-based training and artificial intelligence - lufthansa-aviation-training.com](https://www.lufthansa-aviation-training.com)

¹⁶ [AI copilot enhances human precision for safer aviation | MIT News | Massachusetts Institute of Technology](https://news.mit.edu/2024/ai-copilot-enhances-human-precision-for-safer-aviation-07-24)

5. Critical analysis / evaluation

Regulatory framework: To harness the full potential of AI in pilot training a regulatory framework needs development through close collaboration between aviation training providers, civil aviation authorities as well as technology companies. While the advantages are clear, implementing AI faces hurdles, including regulatory concerns, prohibitive costs, and the need for large, annotated datasets. There is a need of partnerships between AI developers and aviation training institutions.

Upgrade to the training infrastructure: Even though airline operators are investing in modern state of the art aircrafts with many technological advancements, pilot training is mostly outsourced from external aviation training academies. Many of these academies operate independently from the airline operators and are still using legacy platforms fitted with outdated flying training devices and outdated avionics. The procedural training by these devices do not replicate the physical sensations of the flight – thus limiting the effectiveness of the pilots for operational preparedness.

External Funding: The latest generation flight simulators which include six-axis motion systems, control loading systems, advanced visual systems, instructor stations, exact cockpit replicas, and a sophisticated aircraft data package can each cost in the range of \$5 million to \$ 30 million depending upon the level of customization required for a particular aircraft type.

The aviation training academies need funding support to the tune of 100's of millions of dollars. They also need time to upgrade to the latest flight simulators fitted with all the features and gadgets as explained in this research. The adoption of VR/ AR alone in aviation training requires huge investment in the range of \$ 200 Million within the next ten years.

Amelia supports Evidence-Based Training (EBT) and Competency-Based Training and Assessment (CBTA), enabling instructors and organizations to implement best practices established by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) and International Air Transport Association (IATA). The platform provides a comprehensive solution that addresses all aspects of pilot recruitment, training, and career progression.¹⁷

¹⁷ [APC launches Amelia: AI for aviation recruitment, training](#)

Ethical considerations: There is need of a balance between AI and human decision-making as potential over-reliance on AI could have unwanted implications. Placing complete trust in artificial intelligence (AI) and automation may pose risks. For example, the Boeing 737Max incident reveals the dangers that arise due to overdependence on a faulty automated system and undermining the decisions of a skilled pilots. If automation overrules the command of a pilot and such a flight crashes – there are many fundamental questions could be - who is to blame? The aircraft manufacturer, the software developer? the airline or the regulatory body?

The Federal Aviation Administration have laid a roadmap for AI safety assurance, and they state that there is a need to avoid personification and treat AI as a tool, not a human. They emphasize a clear responsibility assignment and avoid human-centric language to maintain a clear understanding of AI's role and limitations in aviation. The journal further states that one has to differentiate between Learned and Learning AI2: Establish distinct safety assurance methodologies for learned (static) AI and learning (dynamic) AI, understanding the difference their respective operational and safety implications

6. Connections

Pilot Training is experiencing revolutionary advancement through the availability of new technologies. Safety within the aviation industry can be further enhanced by ensuring that all pilots are trained to take advantage of the latest training programs.

7. Conclusion

It is quite evident from the research presented above that AI based pilot training can significantly improve competency of the pilots. Training using the modern generation virtual cockpit systems from companies like **Attract Group**¹⁸ have many novel improvements has significantly improved the learning outcomes. The flight simulators used to train the pilots use the exact same software and computers that are used in real aircraft.

Article on application of **Big Data and Artificial Intelligence in Pilot Training** by **M. H. Shaker and A. I. Al-Alawi** confirm that AI & ML are becoming integral parts of flight simulator which enable adaptative learning catering to individual need of each student pilot providing customized training programs that address specific weaknesses and strengths. These flight simulators can mimic cockpits of many aircraft manufacturers, and this feature is very useful to those airline operators who fly aircraft of different make and models as now they can train the pilots in operating a variety of aircraft models at a single training school that is equipped with such an advanced flight simulator. Such training with support from a **Air Traffic Control simulator from FSHud** can ensure pilots are exposed to realistic situations while taking off and landing – as that is when most of the accidents take place.

The spatial and sensory experiences using VR including the dynamics of flight control systems makes aviation training more effective and engaging. This allows the pilots to develop an appreciation and understanding of distances, heights, and spatial position of the aircraft from other objects and shapes. The student pilots can learn the steps, SOP's as well as practise mitigating actions with minimal risks. They can repeatedly practise, rehearse and test themselves until they gain the required level of competence and confidence.

The AI systems analyze extensive data from training sessions to identify potential weak points in a pilot's responses. Predictive analytics can foresee safety issues and proactively address them during training. For instance, AI-driven models can simulate scenarios that challenge pilots' understanding of risk, improving their ability to react to high-stakes situations. The real-time

¹⁸ [How the US is Transforming Pilot Training with Cutting-Edge Software | Revolutionizing the Skies | Attract Group](#)

feedback features can point out if pilots are focusing their attention on key parameters through feeding weather patterns, air traffic and fuel consumption, performance of all sensors and controls.

Use of AI in aviation training will contribute to broader safety culture by assisting in situational analysis and decision making. AI systems can flag overlooked procedures and offer corrective steps in complex situations thus reducing human errors.

Time to train is a very significant factor as the time required to be a competent pilot is very high close to 2.5 year and 1500 hours of flying. A cohort of 58 flight students at **Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University** successfully decreased the duration required to accomplish their inaugural solo flight by over 30 percent, attributable to an innovative general aviation flight training program utilizing VR and AR methodologies.¹⁹

8. Identify gaps in the literature

The available literature does not explain the costs and timeline when the whole aviation industry can implement such AI based trainings.

It does not list the regulatory framework and will of the civil aviation authorities in implementing such training programs.

9. Suggest areas for future research.

Future research can consider estimating costs as well as list the infrastructure required by the aviation industry to deploy such AI based trainings.

The industry must keep an eye on the future as well monitoring the evolving role of AI in next-generation aviation and how it can be integrated with autonomous and semi-autonomous flight systems.

¹⁹ [Improved Pilot-Training Program Yields Promising Results](#)

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